

1 **Is there any direct link between hazardous trace metals and the allantoin content in**
2 **moss species?**

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17

18 **Abstract**

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20 The accumulation of allantoin and trace metals (TMs) in nine moss species were examined after
21 the exposure to stress conditions. Both the environmental anthropopressure effect and
22 laboratory-simulated stress conditions were monitored. Moss samples were collected from
23 different locations, i.e. a non-TM contaminated area, an urban area, and a metalliferous area.
24 The effect of Cd, Pb, Hg, Ni, Zn, salinity, and an acidic environment on the allantoin content
25 was tested. Principal component analysis was performed to reveal the relationship between
26 samples of different origin. Large differences in the metal and allantoin accumulation capability
27 of mosses were noted between samples harvested from the different locations. Seven species
28 were considered as potential hyperaccumulators, as they exhibited tolerance to elevated levels
29 of heavy metals. The observed TM effect on the allantoin accumulation indicated TM pollution
30 as an important environmental factor that can significantly influence the content of this
31 compound in mosses. Further studies on the contribution of various environmental factors and
32 individual characteristics of plant species are highly expected to recognise the trend in the
33 accumulation of specialized metabolites and TMs in response to hazardous growth conditions.

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1. Introduction

Adverse environmental conditions, such as hazardous trace metal (TM) pollution, can considerably affect plant secondary metabolism. Due to the metabolic plasticity, one of the strategies of plants to reduce the negative impact of TM excess is their ability to accumulate plant specialized metabolites such as ligands, antioxidants, or signaling agents (Dixon and Paiva, 1995; Kováčik et al., 2009; Dresler et al., 2017a). Over the past decade, allantoin – a derivative of purine, become attractive as a plant stress mitigation compound (Dresler et al., 2022; Kaur et al., 2021; Nourimand and Todd, 2016).

Allantoin is a natural compound present in several plant families, including Boraginaceae (Dresler et al., 2017b) and Fabaceae (Hanaka et al., 2019a). Additionally, allantoin has been detected in rice (Wang et al., 2012), *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Dresler et al., 2022; Irani and Todd, 2016; Nourimand and Todd, 2019), lichens (Dresler et al., 2021), algae, and fungi (Barash, 1972; Piedras et al., 1998). Besides its role in assimilation, transport, and storage of nitrogen, this molecule is considered as an important mediator of plant stress (Lescano et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2012). When applied exogenously to the growth medium, allantoin enhanced tolerance to metals (Dresler et al., 2019; Dresler et al., 2021b) or salinity (Irani et al., 2018) in plants. It was previously noticed that the level of endogenous allantoin in plants was significantly elevated in response to heavy metal pollution, e.g., with Cd or Hg (Dresler et al., 2017a; 2022; Nourimand and Todd, 2016). This reaction was linked to the activation of the enzymatic antioxidant system and to the increase in the ascorbic acid and glutathione contents in *aln3 Arabidopsis* mutants. It has been found that *Echium vulgare* exposed to an excess dose of metals accumulated from 10- to 20-fold higher amounts of allantoin in roots, compared to non-stressed plants (Dresler et al., 2017a). It has also been reported that different lichen species collected from locations exhibiting a high level of anthropopressure accumulated significantly higher amounts of allantoin compared to control samples (Dresler et al., 2021a). On the other hand, allantoin has been listed as a mediator in activation of the microbial community in contaminated soils (Wang et al., 2010, 2007). Interestingly, its presence led to an increased number of growth-promoting endophytes in cucumber plants exposed to Cd (Dresler et al., 2021b). Since a positive correlation between the anthropopressure level, in particular TM pollution, and the allantoin content in both higher plant and lichen species has been noticed, allantoin may be considered as a TM stress mitigation factor and as an environmental pollution indicator (Dresler et al., 2018; Dresler et al., 2021a). It should be emphasized at the same time that allantoin exerts a heavy metal-dependent and species-specific effect (Dresler et al., 2021a).

1 Allantoin contained in mosses may be an important bioindicator of anthropogenic pressure
2 on the natural environment. As mosses did not develop a well-defined cuticle, ions, including
3 TMs from wet/dry deposition, can be easily absorbed and accumulated (Gstoettner and Fisher,
4 1997). The high ability of mosses to retain TMs from the environment suggest that moss
5 species can be regarded as hyperaccumulators (Vukojević et al., 2005) or indicators in
6 assessment of TM contamination (Tipping et al., 2008). On the other hand, mosses are
7 considered to be rich in bioactive compounds of different classes, such as phenylpropanoids,
8 terpenoids, or steroids; however, no alkaloids, including allantoin, have been reported so far
9 (Zinsmeister et al., 1991; Sabovljević et al., 2016). Therefore, the main goal of the study was
10 to assess the content of allantoin in various species of mosses. Nine moss species collected
11 from different locations of Poland were studied. Based on quantitative analyses of the
12 allantoin content and TM accumulation in the moss samples, the anthropopressure
13 phenomenon was investigated in terms of the effect of the metal pollution on the allantoin
14 content. Moreover, in a short-term laboratory experiment, the effect of selected TMs (Cd, Pb,
15 Hg, Ni, Zn), salinity, and acidic environment (stimulated acid rain conditions) on the allantoin
16 content in two chosen moss species was examined.

17 18 **2. Materials and methods**

19 *2.1. Sample collection and description of research sites*

20 The samples of nine moss species were collected from 12 different locations in Southern
21 Poland (Suppl. Fig. 1, Table 1). Additionally, another 20 species were collected only from an
22 urban area or non-contaminated references sites (Suppl. Table 1). In all selected locations, the
23 soil samples were also collected for evaluation of the TM content. In terms of heavy metal
24 contamination, which reflects the anthropopressure level, the harvest sites were divided into
25 three groups – non-contaminated (reference/control) areas (R1-R4), contaminated urban areas
26 (C1-C3), and contaminated metalliferous areas (M1-M5). The reference sites with a low level
27 anthropopressure were located in South-Eastern Poland, mostly in a forest or wasteland, far
28 from human households, main communications routes, or heavy industries. The other two
29 harvest sites with a higher anthropopressure level were located in three urban areas: Sanok,
30 Lublin, and Cracow. Sanok is inhabited by approx. 40,000 people. In 2018, there were 40 days
31 of PM₁₀ (particulate matter) exceedance in the air ($50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (<https://powietrze.gios.gov.pl>).
32 Similar observations were noted in Lublin, where approx. 340,000 inhabitants live and 40
33 days of PM₁₀ exceedance in the air was reported in 2018. In turn, in Cracow, which has
34 approx. 760,000 inhabitants, over a hundred days of PM₁₀ exceedance was noted in 2018.

1 The highly polluted areas, mainly by heavy metals, were regarded as metalliferous sites. Here,
2 two Zn-Pb mining and smelting waste deposits were selected. The first one (M1) is a relatively
3 old (90-year-old) waste metalliferous heap formed by byproducts of gravitational enrichment
4 of Zn and Pb ores. The other metalliferous waste heap (M2) is a 30-year-old waste slag deposit
5 left over a former Pb-Zn smelter. Furthermore, two metallurgic complexes: a copper smelter
6 Legnica (M3) and a Zn-Pb smelter in Miasteczko Śląskie (M5) were selected as highly TM
7 polluted areas. The last site (M4) located in Siechnice near Wrocław is a slag heap formed as
8 a result of the activity of a ferrochrome smelter closed down in 1990 (Łukasik et al., 2021).

10 2.2. Allantoin identification and analysis

11 80 mg of dry moss samples was homogenized in a mortar with addition of 2 mL of
12 deionized water. Next, the mixture was placed in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min at 50 °C. After
13 the ultrasonic extraction, the homogenates were centrifuged at 10,000 g for 3 min. Prior to the
14 analysis, the supernatants were filtered through a 0.22 µm membrane filter. The quantification
15 of allantoin in the moss extracts was conducted using high-performance liquid
16 chromatography coupled with a diode array detector (VWR Hitachi Chromaster 600 Merck,
17 Darmstadt Germany) and with separation on the Rezex ROA-Organic H+ (8%) LC column
18 (300 × 7.8 mm). The concentration of allantoin was calculated based on absorption obtained
19 at 195 nm. The identity of allantoin was confirmed by comparison of the retention time and
20 spectral similarity with the allantoin standard. Additionally, allantoin was identified in the
21 mosses using the capillary electrophoresis method (Agilent 7100 Capillary Electrophoresis,
22 Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) coupled with a diode array detector according
23 to a method described before (Dresler et al., 2021). Moreover, a comparison of mass spectra
24 between the samples and the allantoin standard was conducted using an Agilent Technology
25 1290 Infinity Series II ultra-high performance liquid chromatograph equipped an Agilent 6224
26 ESI/TOF mass detector (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) (Suppl. Figure 2).

28 2.3. Metal assay

29 The TM contents in the soil and moss samples were measured. The mineralization and ICP-
30 OES analysis of metals were performed according to a method described previously (Dresler
31 et al., 2019a). Briefly, the moss samples were digested in a mixture of HNO₃ and H₂O (2:8
32 v/v) using microwave digestion apparatus (TOPwave Analytick Jena AG, Jena, Germany).
33 Similarly, the soil samples were digested using the microwave digestion apparatus in a
34 mixture of HNO₃ and H₂O (1:1 v/v). The accumulation of metals in the mineralizates was

1 estimated using an ICP-OES Plasma Quant PQ Elite instrument (Analytik Jena AG, Jena,
2 Germany).

3 4 2.4. Simulated exposure to stress factors

5 Both *Hypnum cupressiforme* and *Plagiomnium cuspidatum* collected from the Mircze site
6 (R3) were used in short-term laboratory experiments performed with the method described
7 previously (Dresler et al., 2021a). Briefly, 50 mg of air-dried mosses incubated in 25 mL of 5
8 mM HEPES aq. buffer (pH 6.5) were exposed to 100 μM of chloride forms of Cd, Pb, Hg, Ni,
9 or Zn (all from Sigma-Aldrich, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) for 24 h. Moreover, the
10 moss samples were exposed to salinity (50 mM NaCl) or 3.0 pH (HEPES buffer adjusted
11 using HNO_3). Moss samples incubated in HEPES buffer only were considered as a control.
12 After 24 h of incubation at PAR $\sim 30 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, the samples were dried using filter paper
13 and the allantoin content was measured. The absolute dry mass of the moss samples was
14 evaluated based on the weight of sub-samples dried in an oven at 105 °C.

1 **Table 1.** List of sampling sites with the content of heavy metals in the soil. (R) – reference areas with a low
 2 anthropopressure level; (C) – urban areas; (M) – metalliferous areas
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Abbreviation	Location	Location details	Coordinates DMS	Soil heavy metal content ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)
R1	Sanocko-Turczańskie Mountains, Olchowski Stream	Woodland edge	N 49°33'28.4" E 22°15'06.0"	Ag 0.029; Cd 1.628; Cr 3.275; Cu 23.09; Ni 17.76; Pb 32.21; Tl 1.532; Zn 79.09
R2	Sanocko-Turczańskie Mountains, Sobień Mountain	Woodland edge	N 49°31'37.3" E 22°19'37.2"	Ag 0.075; Cd 0.880; Cr 11.21; Cu 30.50; Ni 8.391; Pb 31.34; Tl 0.192; Zn 79.51
R3	Mircze	Forest	N 50°39'39.7" E 23°52'22.8"	Ag 0.104; Cd 0.359; Cr 5.925; Cu 17.37; Ni 8.069; Pb 15.65; Tl 0.705; Zn 47.93
R4	Sanok suburbs	Woodland edge	N 49°34'16.5" E 22°10'45.0"	Ag 0.032; Cd 0.312; Cr 10.12; Cu 17.51; Ni 12.88; Pb 13.58; Tl 0.051; Zn 60.59
C1	Sanok center	Urban area	N 49°31'37.3" E 22°19'37.2"	Ag 0.215; Cd 0.362; Cr 21.86; Cu 19.54; Ni 13.16; Pb 164.3; Tl 0.199; Zn 305.9
C2	Lublin center	Urban area	N 51°14'37.7" E 22°32'37.9"	Ag 0.371; Cd 0.375; Cr 22.41; Cu 14.14; Ni 9.538; Pb 23.13; Tl 0.258; Zn 79.51
C3	Cracow center	Urban area	N 50°03'54.7" E 19°56'44.8"	Ag 0.172; Cd 5.72; Cr 124.2; Cu 15.27; Ni 11.23; Pb 74.94; Tl 0.413; Zn 180.59
M1	Piekary Śląskie – Brzozowiec Kamień District	Pb-Zn waste heap	N 50°21'54.7" E 18°58'10.4"	Ag 82.94; Cd 632.7; Cr 30.31; Cu 277.8; Ni 88.32; Pb 3280; Tl 15.86; Zn 72540
M2	Piekary Śląskie – Dołki District	Pb-Zn waste heap	N 50°21'12.1" E 19°00'12.2"	Ag 12.59; Cd 344.7; Cr 32.25; Cu 15.96; Ni 45.25; Pb 14903; Tl 16.25; Zn 89170
M3	Legnica	Cu smelter	N 51°11'09.7" E 16°05'52.0"	Ag 19.95; Cd 7.13; Cr 31.51; Cu 4703; Ni 34.72; Pb 3166; Tl 4.18; Zn 914.2
M4	Wrocław - Sichenice	Cr waste heap	N 51°02'32.2" E 17°07'48.6"	Ag 0.082; Cd 0.227; Cr 412.2; Cu 16.26; Ni 42.75; Pb 16.10; Tl 0.615; Zn 212.3
M5	Miasteczko Śląskie	Zn-Pb smelter	N 50°30'32.4" E 18°56'31.7"	Ag 5.691; Cd 339.3; Cr 17.36; Cu 200.3; Ni 21.01; Pb 6857; Tl 33.03; Zn 10828

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 5 *2.5. Statistical analysis*
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7 Three samples of each moss species were collected from the selected sites. Based on one-
 8 way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$), the difference between the
 9 locations within the same species was evaluated. Additionally, Pearson's correlation
 10 coefficients were used to evaluate the relationship between the TM content and allantoin
 11 accumulation in the moss species. In order to visualize the allantoin content, the relative
 12 content of TMs presented in linear bars was expressed using Microsoft Excel (version 22.07).
 13 The impact of stress factors evaluated in the control conditions in the laboratory experiment
 14 was evaluated using t-test. The principal component analysis (PCA) was performed based on

1 the content of allantoin and metals accumulated in the different species. All statistical analyses
2 were performed using Statistica ver. 13.3 (Tibco Software Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA).

3 4 5 **3. Results and discussion**

6 7 *3.1. Location of mosses and accumulation of metals*

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9 Nine of the 29 tested moss species were collected from at least 2 locations differing in the
10 anthropopressure level and TM pollution: non-TM contaminated sites (R1-R4), urban areas
11 (C1-C3), and/or metalliferous sites (M1-M5) (Table 1, 2, Suppl. Table 1). Seven species,
12 namely *B. rutabulum*, *B. salebrosum*, *B. caespiticium*, *C. purpureus*, *H. cupressiforme*, *P.*
13 *schreberi*, and *T. muralis*, exhibited tolerance to high levels of TMs as they originated from
14 the highly TM-polluted areas and were found in the metalliferous sites (Table 2). The metal
15 accumulation capability of the moss species varied widely and significantly between samples
16 collected from the different harvest sites. The presented data confirm the high ability of
17 mosses to accumulate TMs and indicate that some species may be considered as
18 hyperaccumulators (Baker and Brooks, 1989). For instance, *B. salebrosum*, *H. cupressiforme*,
19 and *P. schreberi* accumulate Cu, while *B. caespiticium* and *C. purpureus* allocate Cd, Pb, and
20 Zn more preferably. These data are in agreement with an earlier report on metal accumulation
21 by *Bryum capillare* and *C. purpureus* collected from a coal ash disposal site (Vukojević et al.,
22 2005). However, it should be noted that the highest TM accumulation was observed only in
23 individuals collected from the metalliferous areas characterized by a high level of TM
24 pollution (cf. Tables 1 and 2).

Table 2. Mean (\pm SD) content of metals in moss species

Species	Location	Ag [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Cd [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Cr [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Cu [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Ni [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Pb [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Tl [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Zn [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Fe [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	K [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Mg [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]	Ca [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]
Brachythecium rutabulum (Hedw.) Schimp.	R2	nd	0.33 \pm 0.04	2.34 \pm 0.30	10.58 \pm 0.57	1.24 \pm 0.37	2.74 \pm 0.52	nd	51.90 \pm 5.80	0.38 \pm 0.07	8.37 \pm 0.40	1.45 \pm 0.02	11.64 \pm 0.04
	R3	nd	0.13 \pm 0.02	0.72 \pm 0.15	12.62 \pm 8.13	0.79 \pm 0.16	2.09 \pm 0.09	nd	24.69 \pm 9.19	0.26 \pm 0.11	13.22 \pm 0.78	1.79 \pm 0.30	8.11 \pm 2.00
	C1	nd	0.22 \pm 0.01	2.81 \pm 0.80	8.57 \pm 0.20	1.77 \pm 0.39	5.07 \pm 0.87	nd	106.28 \pm 8.43	1.00 \pm 0.30	6.59 \pm 0.38	1.27 \pm 0.05	11.25 \pm 0.65
	C2	nd	0.18 \pm 0.00	4.60 \pm 0.24	8.52 \pm 0.11	4.76 \pm 0.41	4.04 \pm 0.34	nd	46.22 \pm 0.32	2.48 \pm 0.27	7.37 \pm 0.33	1.95 \pm 0.08	10.60 \pm 0.02
	C3	nd	0.32 \pm 0.01	9.69 \pm 0.40	15.74 \pm 0.41	3.64 \pm 0.15	108.60 \pm 11.70	nd	174.40 \pm 19.70	2.50 \pm 0.01	10.87 \pm 0.39	1.86 \pm 0.02	10.99 \pm 0.40
	M4	0.19 \pm 0.01	12.56 \pm 0.13	49.04 \pm 0.91	22.27 \pm 2.38	21.13 \pm 4.23	15.29 \pm 3.62	0.332 \pm 0.172	68.13 \pm 1.26	3.12 \pm 0.13	8.22 \pm 0.36	3.12 \pm 0.13	10.62 \pm 1.42
Brachythecium salebrosum	R3	nd	0.14 \pm 0.01	1.41 \pm 0.23	5.08 \pm 0.57	1.14 \pm 0.31	2.45 \pm 0.65	nd	20.21 \pm 0.41	0.41 \pm 0.16	8.62 \pm 0.56	2.23 \pm 0.06	8.07 \pm 0.18
	C1	nd	0.55 \pm 0.06	6.79 \pm 0.29	11.71 \pm 0.17	6.08 \pm 0.34	8.47 \pm 0.49	nd	66.22 \pm 2.81	4.82 \pm 0.32	10.08 \pm 0.13	3.44 \pm 0.10	6.19 \pm 0.73
	C2	nd	0.19 \pm 0.02	1.92 \pm 0.10	10.25 \pm 0.42	1.29 \pm 0.08	4.40 \pm 0.28	nd	55.35 \pm 1.55	0.77 \pm 0.03	7.39 \pm 0.08	1.13 \pm 0.02	9.50 \pm 0.09
	M3	0.16 \pm 0.02	0.25 \pm 0.05	1.19 \pm 0.06	1161.84 \pm 68.63	2.83 \pm 0.52	6.40 \pm 0.24	nd	62.22 \pm 2.50	1.24 \pm 0.54	5.83 \pm 0.94	2.16 \pm 0.04	5.14 \pm 0.40
Bryum caespiticium Hedw.	C1	nd	0.27 \pm 0.01	7.74 \pm 1.30	11.49 \pm 0.56	8.43 \pm 1.31	6.74 \pm 1.52	nd	54.34 \pm 3.08	5.35 \pm 0.98	6.96 \pm 0.42	2.54 \pm 0.19	14.58 \pm 0.06
	C2	nd	0.32 \pm 0.06	3.51 \pm 0.05	10.10 \pm 0.24	1.70 \pm 0.20	4.22 \pm 0.47	nd	47.82 \pm 0.27	1.01 \pm 0.21	7.19 \pm 0.34	0.85 \pm 0.01	9.78 \pm 0.05
	M1	25.80 \pm 0.07	346.40 \pm 1.30	12.27 \pm 0.23	126.95 \pm 1.85	29.60 \pm 0.61	13707.00 \pm 259.00	6.58 \pm 0.04	28960.00 \pm 629.00	57.47 \pm 1.27	3.92 \pm 0.11	3.97 \pm 0.06	11.33 \pm 0.17
	M5	5.69 \pm 0.55	524.25 \pm 12.65	10.22 \pm 0.59	240.35 \pm 27.85	11.63 \pm 1.16	6741.00 \pm 590.00	155.95 \pm 21.95	13386.50 \pm 207.50	1.40 \pm 0.16	11.61 \pm 0.62	2.20 \pm 0.18	5.63 \pm 0.17
Ceratodon purpureus	R5	nd	0.45 \pm 0.00	3.79 \pm 0.07	14.20 \pm 0.50	2.37 \pm 0.11	4.81 \pm 0.64	nd	33.02 \pm 1.01	1.55 \pm 0.09	4.67 \pm 0.32	0.95 \pm 0.08	12.37 \pm 0.66
	C2	nd	4.97 \pm 0.21	9.27 \pm 1.79	17.70 \pm 0.09	9.68 \pm 2.29	13.79 \pm 2.26	nd	73.26 \pm 10.06	5.70 \pm 1.63	6.28 \pm 0.64	2.20 \pm 0.16	6.85 \pm 0.35
	M2	4.93 \pm 0.56	154.20 \pm 20.90	15.10 \pm 1.63	11.14 \pm 0.50	19.31 \pm 2.28	6813.00 \pm 934.00	8.82 \pm 1.95	33528.00 \pm 4524.00	73.70 \pm 10.20	3.35 \pm 0.36	7.13 \pm 1.03	19.56 \pm 2.58
	M4	0.31 \pm 0.10	0.22 \pm 0.01	100.07 \pm 13.33	9.54 \pm 0.47	31.91 \pm 3.81	37.17 \pm 1.36	nd	42.25 \pm 0.93	5.92 \pm 0.78	6.15 \pm 0.05	2.73 \pm 0.27	11.40 \pm 0.79
	M5	3.50 \pm 0.21	403.00 \pm 57.50	6.80 \pm 0.34	149.70 \pm 8.10	8.32 \pm 0.31	4392.00 \pm 215.00	102.10 \pm 17.31	10635.50 \pm 1232.50	1.32 \pm 0.01	10.68 \pm 0.45	1.57 \pm 0.15	9.78 \pm 0.93
Hypnum cupressiforme Hedw.	R1	nd	0.34 \pm 0.02	1.28 \pm 0.31	5.01 \pm 0.27	3.89 \pm 0.37	5.31 \pm 0.66	nd	35.19 \pm 0.92	0.35 \pm 0.04	3.99 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.01	7.15 \pm 0.20
	R3	nd	0.22 \pm 0.01	5.41 \pm 0.74	8.18 \pm 0.31	5.13 \pm 0.68	9.38 \pm 1.20	nd	26.01 \pm 1.28	3.28 \pm 0.60	4.24 \pm 0.06	1.16 \pm 0.07	4.71 \pm 0.03
	R4	nd	0.31 \pm 0.01	3.55 \pm 0.11	6.84 \pm 0.60	3.12 \pm 0.39	5.02 \pm 0.38	nd	27.96 \pm 1.47	2.18 \pm 0.29	4.09 \pm 0.19	1.65 \pm 0.06	7.23 \pm 0.12
	C3	nd	1.26 \pm 0.12	5.30 \pm 0.58	19.34 \pm 0.09	2.50 \pm 0.33	17.26 \pm 1.82	nd	138.10 \pm 1.00	2.19 \pm 0.42	6.46 \pm 0.32	1.59 \pm 0.00	8.31 \pm 0.45
	M3	0.22 \pm 0.04	0.20 \pm 0.01	0.80 \pm 0.00	1025.32 \pm 53.57	2.39 \pm 0.00	4.60 \pm 0.19	nd	36.66 \pm 3.80	0.52 \pm 0.04	4.34 \pm 0.25	2.11 \pm 0.03	4.44 \pm 0.12
Orthotrichum anomalum	R1	nd	0.34 \pm 0.00	0.81 \pm 0.01	6.27 \pm 0.19	1.65 \pm 0.17	3.40 \pm 0.04	nd	32.52 \pm 0.06	0.24 \pm 0.01	21.42 \pm 0.36	0.86 \pm 0.01	3.20 \pm 0.07
	R5	nd	0.57 \pm 0.05	5.02 \pm 1.06	10.21 \pm 2.03	4.07 \pm 1.31	9.87 \pm 1.47	nd	55.10 \pm 19.35	2.70 \pm 1.00	4.58 \pm 0.01	1.34 \pm 0.21	14.93 \pm 0.95
	C2	0.71 \pm 0.53	1.24 \pm 0.06	19.08 \pm 0.03	34.14 \pm 1.69	9.59 \pm 0.31	122.20 \pm 1.00	nd	225.50 \pm 2.00	7.64 \pm 0.32	4.32 \pm 0.35	2.12 \pm 0.13	12.76 \pm 0.01
Plagiommium undulatum (Hedw.) T.J. Kop.	R1	nd	0.27 \pm 0.02	1.12 \pm 0.02	5.31 \pm 0.12	1.87 \pm 0.04	3.97 \pm 0.21	nd	25.64 \pm 0.35	0.57 \pm 0.03	13.88 \pm 0.88	1.38 \pm 0.07	5.28 \pm 0.08
	C3	0.35 \pm 0.06	70.66 \pm 0.33	2.91 \pm 0.23	20.32 \pm 0.16	3.23 \pm 0.24	8.21 \pm 0.11	nd	70.05 \pm 0.31	1.45 \pm 0.18	12.93 \pm 0.04	1.37 \pm 0.00	10.59 \pm 0.19
Pleurozium schreberi (Willd. ex Brid.) Mitt.	R1	nd	0.41 \pm 0.00	1.42 \pm 0.20	6.66 \pm 0.00	2.30 \pm 0.11	4.39 \pm 0.23	nd	32.55 \pm 0.13	0.37 \pm 0.01	11.81 \pm 0.22	1.22 \pm 0.02	6.30 \pm 0.06
	C1	nd	0.52 \pm 0.00	2.60 \pm 1.44	9.57 \pm 1.53	3.26 \pm 0.52	5.72 \pm 0.85	nd	60.47 \pm 2.75	1.16 \pm 0.57	8.67 \pm 1.77	1.88 \pm 0.13	6.95 \pm 2.53
	M3	0.21 \pm 0.04	0.18 \pm 0.02	0.69 \pm 0.16	1359.32 \pm 49.27	1.64 \pm 0.04	3.92 \pm 0.58	nd	23.84 \pm 0.64	0.42 \pm 0.08	4.64 \pm 0.08	1.68 \pm 0.05	3.32 \pm 0.10
Tortula muralis	C1	nd	0.29 \pm 0.03	5.10 \pm 0.54	6.92 \pm 0.01	3.76 \pm 0.01	5.00 \pm 0.36	nd	28.08 \pm 1.88	2.35 \pm 0.04	5.36 \pm 0.02	1.54 \pm 0.06	7.44 \pm 0.38
	C3	0.19 \pm 0.04	0.85 \pm 0.09	10.61 \pm 1.59	34.92 \pm 5.09	7.05 \pm 0.17	42.11 \pm 10.53	nd	202.15 \pm 27.05	4.17 \pm 0.64	6.65 \pm 0.38	1.44 \pm 0.02	9.62 \pm 0.58
	M4	0.59 \pm 0.10	0.31 \pm 0.10	276.1 \pm 25.0	20.12 \pm 2.01	18.32 \pm 2.10	17.11 \pm 2.01	2.02 \pm 0.13	115.83 \pm 5.53	3.93 \pm 0.11	1.26 \pm 0.25	6.07 \pm 1.01	32.24 \pm 2.04

3.2. Allantoin content in mosses collected from different areas

Three different techniques were applied to confirm the presence of allantoin in the moss species (Suppl. Fig. 2). All the 29 investigated moss species contained a detectable amount of allantoin in the range from 0.06 up to 3.5 mg·g DW⁻¹ (Table 3, Suppl. Table 1). The values of the allantoin content in the mosses were generally lower than in Boraginaceae and lichen species (Dresler et al., 2017b; Dresler et al., 2021a). However, similarly to lichens (Dresler et al., 2021a), the accumulation of allantoin was strongly dependent on the anthropopressure level, which was reflected by the TM content (Table 3). Regardless of the moss species, a similar pattern of the allantoin content was demonstrated. Generally, the individuals collected from the metalliferous or highly polluted urban areas contained a higher amount of TMs and accumulated much more allantoin than samples harvested from the reference areas. Interestingly, the mosses showed great variability of the allantoin content in response to the TM accumulation level. For example, *B. caespitium* collected from the M5 location accumulated 52-fold higher amounts of allantoin than samples collected from the C2 site, in which the TM content was relatively low. The phenomenon of at least a dozen-fold allantoin higher content in response to TMs was also observed in other species, e.g. *P. schreberi* (12-fold increase), *B. salebrosum* (17-fold increase), *H. cupressiforme* (30-fold increase), and *O. anomalum* (52-fold increase). Similar observations were reported for lichen species (Dresler et al., 2021c), where an increased anthropopressure level (i.e., higher TM pollution) significantly elevated the allantoin content. It was noted that strong anthropopressure, including exposure to TMs, resulted in higher allantoin content, i.e. 22-fold higher in *Parmelia sulcata* and 11-fold higher in *Xantoria parietina*, compared to the results of individuals collected from sites with a lower anthropopressure effect (Dresler et al., 2021c). Also, allantoin accumulation was elevated in higher plants collected from a metalliferous waste heap (Dresler et al., 2017a). In unfavorable environmental conditions, such as TM excess, the content of allantoin in the roots and shoots of *Echium vulgare* was 10- and 4-fold higher than in control plants (Dresler et al., 2017a).

1 **Table 3.** Mean (\pm SD) content of allantoin in moss species collected in different locations (n = 3). Values followed
 2 by different letters are significantly different within the same species according to Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$). The
 3 metal contents in the mosses were expressed as linear bars within the same species.

Species	Site	Allantoin $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ DW	Relative metal contents
<i>Brachythecium rutabulum</i> (Hedw.) Schimp. 	R2	0.519 \pm 0.043 c	Ag Cd Cr Cu Ni Pb Tl Zn Fe
	R3	0.590 \pm 0.108 c	
	C1	0.257 \pm 0.029 d	
	C2	0.251 \pm 0.029 d	
	C3	0.773 \pm 0.009 b	
	M4	1.872 \pm 0.112 a	
<i>Brachythecium salebrosum</i> 	R3	0.682 \pm 0.028 d	Ag Cd Cr Cu Ni Pb Tl Zn Fe
	C1	1.464 \pm 0.103 c	
	C2	0.187 \pm 0.028 b	
	M3	3.358 \pm 0.051 a	
<i>Bryum caespiticium</i> Hedw. 	C1	0.183 \pm 0.001 c	Ag Cd Cr Cu Ni Pb Tl Zn Fe
	C2	0.021 \pm 0.003 c	
	M1	0.505 \pm 0.110 b	
	M5	1.095 \pm 0.111 a	
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i> 	R5	0.209 \pm 0.050 d	Ag Cd Cr Cu Ni Pb Tl Zn Fe
	C2	0.281 \pm 0.023 d	
	M2	0.726 \pm 0.056 c	
	M4	0.886 \pm 0.076 bc	
	M5	0.979 \pm 0.147 b	
<i>Hypnum cupressiforme</i> Hedw. 	R1	0.115 \pm 0.019 d	Ag Cd Cr Cu Ni Pb Tl Zn Fe
	R3	0.581 \pm 0.078 c	
	R4	0.389 \pm 0.098 cd	
	C3	0.988 \pm 0.046 b	
	M3	3.439 \pm 0.271 a	
<i>Orthotrichum anomalum</i> 	R1	0.018 \pm 0.000 b	Ag Cd Cr Cu Ni Pb Tl Zn Fe
	R5	0.017 \pm 0.000 b	
	C2	0.929 \pm 0.052 a	

1 **Table 4.** Correlation coefficients between accumulation of metals and allantoin in moss species collected from
 2 different areas (n = 9 – 15)

	<i>Brachythecium rutabulum (Hedw.) Schimp.</i>	<i>Brachythecium salebrosum</i>	<i>Bryum caespiticium Hedw.</i>	<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	<i>Hypnum cupressiforme Hedw.</i>	<i>Orthotrichum anomalum</i>	<i>Pleurozium schreberi</i>	<i>Tortula muralis</i>
Ag	0.920	0.922	ns	0.551	0.951	0.756	ns	ns
Cd	0.922	ns	0.942	0.618	ns	0.957	ns	0.676
Cr	0.929	ns	0.669	ns	ns	0.969	ns	ns
Cu	0.811	0.923	0.975	ns	0.949	0.986	ns	0.856
Ni	0.572	ns	ns	0.532	ns	0.936	0.842	ns
Pb	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.984	ns	0.780
Tl	0.853	-	0.912	0.551	-	-	-	ns
Zn	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.983	0.885	0.858
Fe	0.600	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.932	ns	0.812
K	ns	ns	0.602	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Mg	0.844	ns	ns	ns	0.826	0.892	0.683	ns
Ca	ns	-0.916	-0.712	ns	-0.556	ns	ns	ns

3
 4 The two first factors of the PCA analysis explained between 75 and 97% of the total variance.
 5 Both components facilitated separation of the individuals of all the investigated species in
 6 relation to the collection sites. The results discriminated metalliferous individuals along the
 7 component loaded by TM accumulation in the mosses and, as it turned out, generally the
 8 allantoin content. This phenomenon was observed in *B. rutabulum* (Fig. 1a), *B. selabrosum*
 9 (Fig. 1b), *B. caespiticium* (Fig. 1c), *C. purpureus* (Fig. 1d), *H. cupressiforme* (Fig. 1e), and *O.*
 10 *anomalum* (Fig. 1g), where clear separation of the C2 individuals from both the R1 and R5
 11 samples were noted. In turn, the M3 individuals of *P. schreberi* moss grouped along with factor
 12 1, which was positively correlated with Ag and Cu but negatively correlated with allantoin and
 13 the content of other metals (Fig. 1f). In this case, the mosses collected from the M3 location
 14 exhibited extremely huge Cu accumulation but relatively low (compared to C1) content of the
 15 other TMs, including Cd, Ni, Cr, Pb, or Zn, which were correlated with allantoin and had a
 16 considerable impact on factor 1, which was capable to separate C1 from M3 individuals (Fig.
 17 1f). Similarly, in *T. muralis* (Fig. 1h), the allantoin content together with Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, and
 18 Cd were loaded by factor 2 and distinguished C3 individuals but not M4 – samples with
 19 extremely high accumulation of Cr and a certain amount of Ag, Ni, or Tl. The observed TM
 20 effect on the allantoin accumulation in the moss species showed that TM pollution is an
 21 important factor that can influence the allantoin content in mosses. These findings supported
 22 our earlier studies, where a diversified pattern of accumulation of various heavy metals strongly
 23 affected the allantoin content in lichen species (Dresler et al., 2021a).

1
 2 **Fig. 1.** Principal component analysis (PCA) of TM and allantoins accumulation in different moss species collected
 3 from different locations. (a) *B. rutabulum*; (b) *B. salebrosum*; (c) *B. caespiticium*; (d) *C. purpureus*; (e) *H.*
 4 *cupressiforme*; (f) *P. schreberi*; (g) *O. anomalum*; (h) *T. muralis*
 5

3.3. Effects of simulated stress factors on mosses

To avoid misleading conclusions coming from the multi-factorial environmental study, a highly controlled series of laboratory experiments using simulation of stress factors were performed. The experiments were based on a one-factor effect. The short-term heavy metal exposure significantly elevated the content of allantoin in *H. cupressiforme* (Fig. 2a). The application of Hg resulted in an approx. 3-fold increase in the allantoin content, an approx. 2-fold higher level of Pb and Ni, and a 65 and 90% increase in the Cd and Zn content (Fig. 2a). However, the simulated acidic environment conditions did not affect the allantoin content, while salinity decreased its amount. In turn, the supplementation of Cd, Pb, Hg, and Ni as well as salinity in *P. cuspidatum* had no significant impact on the allantoin content (Fig. 2b). Only the Zn exposure and acidic pH increased allantoin accumulation by approx. 4.5-fold and 5.5, respectively. Diversified allantoin accumulation in different plant species in response to stress factors in laboratory conditions was reported previously (Dresler et al., 2017c; Hanaka et al., 2019b). Studies on the Pb and Zn effect in *E. vulgare* (Dresler et al., 2017c), the Cd effect in *A. thaliana* (Nourimand and Todd, 2016), and the Sr effect in *Glycine max* (Hanaka et al., 2019a) showed stimulated allantoin accumulation. In contrast, exposure of *Phaseolus coccineus* to 50 μ M of Cu did not affect the allantoin content (Hanaka et al., 2022). In turn, the present findings are in line with the results of our research conducted previously on lichens (Dresler et al., 2021a). Four lichen species exposed to various metals responded differently, except in the case of Hg. It seems that the differences between the analyzed species may be the cause of the individual levels of tolerance to metals. Moreover, after exposure to Zn, the non-metal tolerant *E. vulgare* population showed significantly higher allantoin content than the tolerant population (Dresler et al., 2017c). It was suggested that the metal stress could be responsible for the disturbance in the mechanism of the allantoin enzymatic degradation pathway. This assumption was partially confirmed in other investigations on the *aln3 A. thaliana* mutant exposed to Cd (Dresler et al., 2022).

Fig. 2. Effect of short-term (24 h) exposure to individual heavy metals (100 μ M of Cd, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn), salinity (50 mM NaCl), or acidic environment (pH 3.0) on the allantoin content in (a) *H. cupressiforme* and (b) *P. cuspidatum*. Data are means (\pm SE) (n=4), significant difference at p<0.05 (*), p<0.01 (**), p<0.001 (***) compared to the control (Student's t-test).

4. Conclusions

As shown by the data collected so far, the metabolic response of plant organisms to stress conditions may manifest itself in the accumulation of selected compounds, as in the case of allantoin. However, this phenomenon is not yet fully recognized, because the organisms studied so far react with certain tendencies and with a different intensity of the accumulation level. Further research is necessary to verify the contribution of environmental factors and individual characteristics that may affect the accumulation of specialized metabolites produced by plants to combat stress caused by e.g. overexposure to metals.

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Credit author statement

conceptualisation, methodology, supervision, visualisation (SD) writing – original draft (SD, SZ); sample collection (SD, RZ, SZ, BJP); moss species identification (RZ); HPLC analysis (SD, MW, MS, IZ, MK); metal assay (JS, IS); laboratory experiment (AH); review and editing (AH, SZ, BJP, MS, MK, IS).

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